

Table 2. List of included studies with quality score (Down and Black scale modified)

Research	Item 1	Item 2	Item 3	Item 6	Item 7	Item 10	Item 12	Item 15	Item 16	Item 18	Item 20	Item 22	Item 23	Item 25	Total Score (out of 14)
[24]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	12
[42]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	13
[43]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	13
[44]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[33]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[45]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	12
[46]	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	11
[20]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[14]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[47]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[21]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[48]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	12
[49]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	12
[50]	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13
[51]	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	14

Note: 0 = no; 1 = yes; Item 1: clear aim/hypothesis; Item 2: outcome measures clearly described; Item 3: patient characteristics clearly described; Item 6: main findings clearly described; Item 7: measures of random variability provided; Item 10: actual probability values reported; Item 12: participants prepared to participate representative of entire population; Item 15: Blinding of outcome measures; Item 16: analysis completed was planned; Item 18: appropriate statistics; Item 20: valid and reliable outcome measures; Item 22: participants recruited over same period; Item 23: Randomised; Item 25: adjustment made for confounding variables.